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Glucocorticoid resistance features changes in general transcription factor (GTF) expression.

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We discovered using whole transcriptome technology a suite of general transcription factors whose expression was activated in glucocorticoid resistant conditions. These GTFs likely mediate glucocorticoid resistance *in vivo*.